

SEMINAR ARCH 522

**ENERGY POVERTY OF CLIMATE DISPLACED
PEOPLE IN COASTAL AREAS**

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CONTENTS

- **ABSTRACT**

1. INTRODUCTION

2. AIMS

3. OBJECTIVE

4. METHODOLOGY

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

5.1: Climate displaced people and rehabilitation program

5.2: Energy poverty and factors accelerating poverty

5.3: Achieving energy efficiency through architecture

6. CASE STUDY

6.1: Khurushkul Ashrayan Prokolpo

6.2: Questionnaire survey

7. DATA ANALYSIS

7.1: Energy consumed by equipment analysis

7.2: Energy cost by lighting equipment

7.3: DAYLIGHT STANDARDS

7.4: Floor plan analysis

8. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

9. CONCLUSION

10. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

11. REFERENCE

Energy poverty of climate displaced people in coastal areas

ABSTRACT:

Rural life could be easier and more improved with sustainable and energy efficient housing. In Bangladesh, an oversized group of people lives in rural areas and are below the poverty level. So, it's a tricky job to fulfill all their household needs like electricity, gas, or other utilities altogether with their limited income. Specially the low-income group of people must struggle the most, in providing all the primary needs to their families. Move over the natural calamities are also part and parcel of their life. Many people are losing their homes for these calamities, and they are displaced from their original homes. Khurushkul is one of the examples. Here coastal people are displaced for a better life and provided housing facilities. A portion of their annual savings is spent for bearing the energy cost which is not provided by the government. To be specific, 58 percent of rural households are energy poor, where 45 percent that are income poor in Bangladesh. Side by side population problems also fuel these sorts of issues. The solution to this issue can be managed through sustainable housing that not only provides shelter but also improves the quality of life in rural areas. And using technological innovation both in materials and systems that advances the level of energy efficiency and resiliency in homes designed and built today. The housing can be formed by context, culture and vernacularity but fully embracing the technology and idea of domesticity and can make an end to the difficult and uncertain life.

[Douglas F. Barnes; Shahidur R. Khandker; 20 Apr 2016]

Keywords: Poverty, coastal area, rehabilitation program, energy use, climate displaced

1. INTRODUCTION:

Energy poverty has become a burning issue in developing countries like Bangladesh. We keep ignoring the issue and it creates more problems for us. "There is no energy crisis, only a crisis of ignorance." ~ *R. Buckminster Fuller*. This problem must be solved from different angles as it is connected to different aspects like resources, income, quality of life etc. "We simply must balance our demand for energy with our rapidly shrinking resources. By acting now, we can control our future instead of letting the future control us." ~ *Jimmy Carter*.

When we talk specifically about low-income groups, affordability becomes a great concern. On top of that the income versus the expenditure for energy consumption should be compared properly to understand the real scenario. Even with a handsome level of income, there is no saving due to this problem and in some cases the expenditure is more of the income, which ultimately makes their poor condition worse.

Displacement due to disaster occurs when natural hazards, such as flooding and river erosion, force people to leave their households. In least developed countries or regions climate-induced displacement has been felt severely for many reasons like poor infrastructure, poverty, and social constraints. Bangladesh is a low-lying disaster-prone river delta. Population displacement by extreme weather events is not new to Bangladesh. The country experiences yearly displacement of approximately one million people and losses of about 1% of its gross domestic product due to cyclones, floods, and riverbank erosion.

Therefore, the government must take various rehabilitation programs for the displaced people. The housing problem for the people is solved with the initiative but the problem remains alive due to energy expenditure of their day-to-day life. To solve this problem, the housing in the rehabilitation program should be made in such a way that it consumes less energy. There should be provision to utilize solar energy and rain water harvesting and proper natural air and light ventilation. Unfortunately, all these things are ignored in most of the cases. To get relief from energy poverty these factors must be addressed starting from policy level to entire construction level.

[Kenichi Matsui; July 2021]

[Paloma Taltavull de La Paz, Francisco Juárez Tárrega; et al.29 June 2022]

2. AIM:

The climate displaced people are getting government rehabilitation program facilities for housing, but the energy expenses are still burning them down. The aim is to portray the existing tough life of the climate displaced people and thinking a way out of this poverty loop.

3. OBJECTIVE:

The first objective is to portray the existing poverty conditions of the rehabilitation areas and their causes. Next one is to know about the scope of sustainable and energy efficient lifestyle for the coastal people Finding the income and energy expenditure imbalance. Evaluating the existing fenestration system and suggesting a better one for ensuring the energy efficiency. Lastly, thinking about solutions to overcome the current situation and knowing about the mistakes to future rehabilitation projects better. Through achieving these goals, the primary aim to portray the existing life of climate displaced communities, can be achieved. And from there we can have a conclusion to probable solutions and make prevention to such problems.

4. METHODOLOGY:

To achieve the objectives the method needs to be followed are mentioned below. First, identifying the problem of the selected community. Then doing literature review of definitions and theories related to the problem. Parallely, similar case studies can be done to see the real-life problem. Then collecting data from both survey and literature review to do analysis between them. After data analysis is done, new solutions to the existing problem are proposed.

Figure 1: The Outline of Methodology

5. LITERATURE REVIEW:

5.1: Climate displaced people and rehabilitation program

Bangladesh, having 160 million people, is highly vulnerable to climate change and displacement due to sea-level rise. 28% of the population of Bangladesh lives in the coastal regions of the country.

In the decades ahead, it is expected that, being forced by climate change or other similar reasons the number of refugees will be more and more. According to a World Bank report, by 2050 more than 19 million people will become climate refugees in Bangladesh.

The Ashrayan project became the milestone program for the Bangladesh government for the rehabilitation of the climate victims. They got shelter in a separate house and felt relaxed after starting to live in the newly developed Ashrayan project area. But their happiness ended within a short period of time in most of the Ashraya projects. Common problems have been found for inhabitants in the Guchogram, Ashrayan-1, and Ashrayan-2 and other relocation programs which are as follows: The drinking water crisis, unemployment, and economic solvency. During the rehabilitation process in the Ashrayan project, the inhabitants were promised alternative livelihood security by the respective government department, but their dream was shattered due to not providing the job facilities for their survival.

[Mahmuda Begum Meem, 10 October 2021]

5.2: Energy poverty and factors accelerating poverty

Energy poverty happens when energy bills become a high percentage of consumers' income, which affects their capacity to cover other expenditures. If consumers are forced to reduce the energy consumption of their households, that is also termed as poverty, which affects their physical and mental health and well-being.

The energy poverty definitions are based on the form of measurement to clarify the area of energy poverty problem. Boardman (1991) proposed that “a household is in energy poverty when it’s to spend more than 10% of its income on all domestic energy use, including appliances, to heat the household to a level sufficient for health and comfort”. This is often known as the “10% Boardman rule,” under which energy poverty occurs when a household is “unable to get an adequate amount of energy services for 10% of disposable income” (Boardman, 1991). The rule recognizes that not all households need to make the same effort to pay for their energy needs, with a more severe effect on lower-income households (Boardman, 2012).

But considering the geographic location and climate of Bangladesh, this rule can be rephrased as, energy poverty occurs when a household is “unable to obtain an adequate amount of energy services for 7% of disposable income. As In this weather there is no heating cost, and the cooling cost can be minimal with proper consideration of natural air ventilation (30% heating cost

excluding). If we summarize the factors of accelerating poverty of some rural family we will see some common points, such as unemployment, large family, low and unstable income, poor planning in natural resource

Here, one thing is obvious that all the problems are caused by their economic condition. On top of these problems are making their economic condition poorer. So, to make a way out of the situation, their expenditure control on necessary energy (electricity, water) related bills can be one of the important steps.

[Lunyu Xie, Xian Hu, et al. January 2022]

5.3: Achieving energy efficiency through architecture

Energy efficiency is known as the use of less energy to perform the same task and produce the same result. Energy-efficient homes and buildings use less energy to cool and run appliances and electronics.

For achieving energy efficiency through architecture there are some steps we can take to ensure natural light access, natural ventilation maximization, being careful about site considerations and orientation etc. There are also some measures that are indirectly related to the architecture design strategy, such as rain water harvesting, biogas use, use of solar energy etc.

[Md Abdullah Omar, Muhammad Hasanujzaman, November 2021]

6. CASE STUDY:

6.1: Khurushkul Ashrayan Prokolpo

The climate refugees that are shifting and will shift to Khurushkul or towards other refugee projects, are facing or will face some issues. One of the toughest challenges is, to shift their profession to adapt their lifestyle with a new profession. For this reason, the common problem in Khurushkul housing projects is joblessness. The accommodation it has in the project is a sharp contrast to their previous house at Kutubdiapara. Now they are living in an apartment with two rooms, one kitchen space and one toilet and one bathroom in a five storied building.

If we summarize all the problems we will get few things in origin, unemployment, drinking water, paying all the bills and transportation etc.

6.2: Questionnaire survey

The purpose of the survey was to identify the imbalance between their income and expenses of energy bills. 4 families were questioned about their income expenditure and appliances to identify the reason behind their poverty. The result is as follows -

Table 1: Equipment's energy consumption based on four family's usage

Survey question		Family 1	Family 2	Family 3	Family 4
Occupation		Business	Day labor	Business	Business
Family member		05	09	08	06
Monthly income		10,000	20,000	28,000	16,000
Monthly expenditure		10,000	18,000	25,000	16,000
No of appliance	Fan	02	02	02	02
	Light	04	06	05	05
	TV	-	01	01	01
	Fridge	-	-	01	01
	Others	-	-	02	01
Bills	Electricity	300	700	1200	800
	Gas	1300	1500	1850	1500
	Water	60	100	300	200
Bills % over income		16.6%	11.5%	11.96%	15.63%

7. DATA ANALYSIS:

From the survey result we can see that the percentage of energy bills they must pay against their monthly income is 16.6%, 11.5%, 11.96% and 15.63% respectively. Which means an average of 13.9%.

In the literature review segment, it is discussed about the “10% Boardman rule”, which includes the heating and cooling cost of dry and cold climates. In the case of tropical climate this cost should be less than 5%. But in the Khurushkul housing project the cost has gone 13.9% on average. That is why these climate displaced people are not getting out of the endless poverty loop.

Figure 2: Energy bill percentage from total income to evaluate TPR rule.

Energy consumed by equipment analysis:

From a site survey, it is noticed that some of the houses are using energy efficient bulbs (LED) but some are not. And in most of the families the highest energy consumed equipment is light sources. In some cases, the Incandescent bulbs consume 100W. For calculation, the equipment’s energy consumption is made average.

Here, the fan takes 55W, fridge 150W, TV 80W, LED lights 23W and Incandescent bulbs 100W is considered. And the operation hour is calculated from the survey report. And the four families are selected from different floors to get the most accurate data average. From the questionnaire survey the energy consumption data is shown below.

[Ishtiaque Ahmad, Ali Akbar Razon; April 2017]

Table 2: Energy consumption based on equipment type and operation hour

Family	Equipment	Unit usage (W)	No of Equipment	Operation hour (h)	Total usage (W)	Lighting cost (tk)	Percentage on total
Family 1	Fan	45	2	13	182	250	83.33%
	Light	23	4	19			
	TV	-	-	-			
	Fridge	-	-	-			
	Others	-	-	-			
Family 2	Fan	45	2	16	308	580	82.86%
	Light	23	6	23			
	TV	80 (CRT)	1				
	Fridge	-	-	-			
	Others	-	-	-			
Family 3	Fan	45	2	17	520	540	43.33%
	Light	23	5	20			
	TV	45 (LED)	1	2			
	Fridge	120	1	24			
	Others	-	2	4			
Family 4	Fan	45	2	15	455	520	65%
	Light	23	5	22			
	TV	80 (CRT)	1	2			
	Fridge	120	1	24			
	Others	-	1	2			

Energy cost by lighting equipment:

So In every case we can see the amount of energy consumed by light is more than any other equipment. When the reason is investigated, some common problems are seen. The window location, window size, window use and building orientation. They are discussed elaborately below.

The comparison between the expenditure in equipment is shown in the pie chart. In this process the total cost of energy used by the light source is calculated, then percentage of cost is calculated from the total energy cost.

Here, per unit cost is considered as 5.72 taka

1 unit energy is used by kw per hour.

Figure 3: Expenditure by lighting equipment compared with other equipment.

DAYLIGHT STANDARDS:

From BNBC chapter 8 (8.1.5) we can see the guideline the standard illumination requirement in bed rooms is in general 50 Lux and at bed head 150 Lux.

Analyzing the floor plan layout with the window position and amount of light with a mobile app, we can see that the existing light amount does not match with the standard light requirement for rooms set by BNBC.

The results we got from mobile app is as below,

Living room

Kitchen

Toilet

Bedroom with window

Figure 3.1: Amount of light inside the room measured with lux meter.

Figure 3.2: Amount of light inside the room measured with lux meter.

Day light hour vs Active hour:

The total day light hour for Bangladesh is 12.4 hours. Which starts from 6.00 am around (avg of the year). Where the active hour for the residents starts from 7.00-8.00 am. And the active hour ends at 10.00-11.00 pm. So, among the 16 active hours they could use up to 10 hours.

But when we see the light using hours, we can see the light using hours overlap with the daylight hours. The light using hours should not be higher than 6 hours. But we can see the light using hours is higher than 15 hours in every family. This is because the access of daylight is not ensured in the houses and the amount is not sufficient to the required level. For, making is a measurement of the light available in the rooms we used a mobile app that measure the light amount. By using this app, we can see the amount of light in various places are low and some places are totally out of light due to the position of the window.

But is it sure that is the daylight hours could be utilized properly at least 6-10 hours of light using hours can be minimize.

Analyzing the window position form drawings:

Figure 4: Site plan of Khurushkul housing area.

Figure 5: 1st floor plan of the buildings

Figure 6: One unit plan

Floor plan analysis:

As the location of the windows are not appropriate the light sources are used throughout the day and consume a large portion of energy. Moreover, there are some rooms without windows. Making alternate fenestration can be a way out of this problem. Rooms that don't have the option to open outside can be opened in the corridor. In this case, enough light must be ensured on the corridor and privacy should be maintained carefully.

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8. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION:

From the data we got from surveys and secondary sources, it's clear that the people in the housing projects are under energy poverty. This is only one example of many projects. And there will be many more climate refugees and rehabilitation areas in the days to come. Designing the housing projects without the concept of energy efficiency and without proper light and ventilation facilities, making many people energy poor. The cost which they are paying now could be cut into a bearable level with proper planning.

The first thing is to prevent further such mistakes in the housing projects that will take place in future. And ensuring that all the housing facilities are efficient and affordable to the dwellers. These are - natural light access, natural ventilation maximization, being careful about site considerations and orientation etc.

Last but not the least, to redesign the façade without hampering the superstructure to pass light and air in the rooms and other spaces in the projects which are already finished. Also, they should take some measures so that their energy cost becomes less than it is now, they are as below – Rain water harvesting, biogas use, use of solar energy. By ensuring energy efficient housing, we can expect to see coastal climate displaced people coming out of their poverty loop.

In the unit plan the below reforms can be done to increase the opportunity of cross ventilation and increase the inlet of the sunlight during daytime. Which will result in decreasing their energy cost on lightings and fans.

Figure 7: Rethinking fenestration in a unit plan

9. CONCLUSION:

With issues like global warming and climate change the number of climate refugees will go higher day by day. If the rehabilitation program keeps raising energy poverty, this will affect our national economy. The information and problems discussed here are from only one project in Khurushkul. There might be many other issues that affect poverty in other rehabilitation projects which are not included here. All the factors affecting poverty should be considered while making these projects. Regular inspection and analysis of the projects that have already been built, will make the future project better. With proper planning and environmental considerations being addressed, the projects can be the solution to the climate refugee problem without creating further problems.

10. ACKNOWLEDGMENT:

I would like to acknowledge and give my warmest thanks to my supervisor Prof. Dr. Khandaker Shabbir Ahmed and Mohammad Tahjibul Hossain. Their guidance and advice carried me throughout all the stages of writing my project. I also took help from various online available public resources, all of them are mentioned in the reference section.

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